

Improving “Science for Policy” in Austria – charting a way forward

Nov 2024 / Thomas König

Abstract

This paper is written as an input to the upcoming ERA Symposium in Vienna on 21 November 2024, which is the starting point for drafting the respective chapter on “science for policy” in the Austrian ERA National Action Plan 2025-27. It argues that, in order to make use of the framing of “science for policy” as an ecosystem, it is relevant to focus on existing interactions of scientific advice, and to understand those interactions as situated acts of communication. To make “science for policy” more effective, emphasis should be put on learning opportunities. To that end, the paper offers several ideas that could enhance the advice capacity of actors in the ecosystem.

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I am grateful to everyone who discussed the topic of “science for policy” with me in the run-up to this paper. While their input and considerations were invaluable, the paper’s content and any errors within are solely my responsibility.

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Introduction

Not least because of the pandemic, the integration of scientific expertise into policymaking has become a central issue in science policy discussions nationally and at European level – as can be seen from the fact that several reforms in EU-Member States have been undertaken, that it is now part of the European Research Area planning, and object of several capacity building exercises by the European Commission. In some way, this is a belated interest in a set of activities related to the intersection of scientific knowledge and policymaking that have been established at different levels, and that are now objective of for reflection.

This paper aims to delineate what to realistically expect when talking about “science for policy” in Austria. It starts with some (admittedly subjective) observations about the current use of the term, followed by explicating some basic theoretical assumptions underpinning the concept, and operationalizing the concept for a more analytical understanding. It outlines an approach to getting a comprehensive depiction of the different roles and formats of scientific knowledge in policymaking in the Austrian political landscape and ends with an outlook for next steps and a tentative timeline.

The following is at the same time an input to a potential “ERA Action” under the Austrian ERA National Action Plan, as it is a scoping paper for a project at FORWIT that aims to survey formats and structures of scientific policy advice in Austria – an empirical analysis that will start in 2025 as a first step. In a second step, a more evaluative approach of the existing landscape can be undertaken in later years, potentially aided by the European Commission in the context of the ERA Action. Methodologically, this paper aims to be analytical and practical, to chart a way forward towards more awareness (reflexivity) on the topic, and to provide food for discussion at the upcoming ERA Symposium.

Promise and concerns

This section contains few observations regarding the use of “science for policy”. It is neither a literature review nor a fully-fledged account of all the initiatives that are currently going on. Since it is supposed to stimulate discussion, it is written from a rather critical perspective. Thus, it may not be doing fully justice to the nuances of many papers and thinkers out there – but it does so for the purpose of questioning some basic tenets that are currently not clearly highlighted.

The vantage point of this paper is the **promise** that “science for policy” seems to imply, namely, that science is crucial for policymaking in that it can help to provide a better understanding of a given problem, and hence facilitate better decisions. Underneath this promise looms a more fundamental issue – that of the complicated relation between knowledge and power.¹ Even if – for the purpose of keeping this paper simple – this is ignored for the rest of this paper, it needs to be acknowledged that some of their more practical implications (the power of knowledge brokers; the role of vested interests that go along with it; etc.) lurk in the background when talking about “science for policy”.

A sound understanding of a policy problem is a prerequisite for an adequate solution. In that regard, “science for policy” can also be understood as a kinder, tamed version of the intricate power-knowledge-relationship, one that promises more efficient policymaking, but maybe even democratic accountability. But even in this version, several concerns remain. Is science to be understood as equivalent to knowledge? Who is supposed to speak truth to power? Is the political decision-making process as simple as the promise implies?

¹ This is testified in numerous philosophical treatises and histories along the history of modernity. There is no need here to even scratch the surface of written testimonies of this relationship; one only needs to mention the names of Michel Foucault, or Bruno Latour, among many more.

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These questions show that the promise of “science for policy” comes with **concerns** on its own right. First, it lacks modesty. There is a shortcut between sound understanding of a problem and scientific knowledge. Not every problem that can (or shall) be tackled by policy requires “science”, or “scientific knowledge”, or “knowledge that has been produced in a methodologically systematic and sound way”. Indeed, scientific knowledge is only one contributing factor in decision-making.

Another concern with the term is that it lacks specificity. What does “science for policy” mean, really? Too often, neither the goal, nor the means, nor the basic tenets of the concept are explicated. This is not due to a lack of research into different facets of science-policy-interactions, or procedures and formats of knowledge utilization.² Nor is there a lack of more policy-oriented texts and manuals.³ And yet, it seems that deeper analysis into what constitutes “good” “science for policy” is missing (Oliver 2022, 4). Hence, talk about “science for policy” often comes about as a normative idealization of both science and policy.

It appears as if there is a gap between the promise of “science for policy” and the actual understanding about what interactions there are already established. Often, these interactions are only looked at anecdotally, if at all. Recently, however, the notion of “science for policy” has been extended with the term “**ecosystem**”. As noted in a respective document by the European Commission,

„Science-for-policy ecosystem is here understood as a complex of organisational structures and entities, processes, and networks that interact to support the mobilisation, acquisition, synthesis, translation, presentation for use, and application of scientific knowledge in policymaking processes.“
(European Commission 2022, 4, FN8)

The extension seems to alleviate some of the concerns outlined above. It allows for the inclusion of all sorts of interactions between science and policy, and also different formats of utilizing scientific knowledge for policymaking.⁴ The demarcation of the ecosystem can facilitate discussions about what constitutes improvement in the use of evidence within public policy processes and how improved systems for evidence use for policy could be established. However, the discussion cannot stop here; otherwise, the notion of an “ecosystem” will only help to obscure the nuances of different interactions, and will hinder an open exchange about what to realistically expect from “science for policy”.⁵ While the “ecosystem” aims for the broader picture, this take needs to be complemented by a detailed analysis of the specific “**science for policy**” **interactions**.

In other words, what is missing is a closer look into the conceptual premises under which any given interaction between science and policy is taking place when scientific knowledge is supposed to be utilized for policymaking. This asks for a more curious and systematic approach to survey the various types of interaction (“structures and entities, processes, and networks”, as they are called in the quote above) already established. These aspects are crucial to understand how scientific knowledge can be used realistically.

To sum up, “science for policy” is in danger of not living up to its promise, in that it remains at the surface of things, that it remains prescriptive, naïve and even a fig-leave. To escape this danger, it is necessary to take a closer look at some conceptual underpinnings that constitute “science for policy”.

² A recent article identifies several thousand academic articles dealing with the issue (Capano and Malandrino 2022).

³ To name just a few texts that have been published recently on this topic (Kärkkäinen et al. 2024; Šucha and Sienkiewicz 2020; Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften and Nationalen Akademie der Wissenschaften Leopoldina 2023; Delfraissy et al. 2024)

⁴ The term “ecosystem” is nowadays quite popular; there are “cyber security ecosystems”, “innovation ecosystems”, as well as “software ecosystems”.

⁵ See, however, a recent attempt to use the “science-for-policy ecosystems” as a way to assess specific interactions more thoroughly (Pedersen 2023).

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“Science for policy” as a problem space

To get a more analytical understanding of “science for policy”, it is helpful to look at it as a specific “problem space” (Lury 2020). This warrants a brief reflection of its theoretical underpinnings. This starts, first, with a brief reflection on scientific knowledge utilization in the domain of policymaking. It then postulates that “science for policy” is best conceptualized as a situated practice that needs to be understood as an act of communication.

Knowledge utilization, broadly, refers to using scientific knowledge in a specific domain outside academia. Table 1 depicts two different realms of knowledge utilization, one being the economy, the other one the domain of policymaking. This is a highly idealized and top-down depiction so it should be taken with a grain of salt; the purpose is to make explicit that terminology about scientific knowledge utilization is very different in each of these two realms. These notional differences allow for a more accurately grasp of the respective logic of knowledge utilization.

Table 1: Schematic depiction of knowledge utilization in the domain of the economy and in the domain of policymaking.

	(scientific) knowledge used in ...	
	... the economy	... policymaking
Scientific practice	“pre-competitive research”	“regulatory science”
Knowledge translates into	Technology	Expertise
Policy frame	Innovation	Regulation
Expected impact	Productivity, economic growth	Efficiency, sound (evidence-based) decision-making

By TK

In the economic realm, the scientific practice underpinning knowledge utilization can be termed “pre-competitive research”; knowledge is expected to result in technology of some sort; and this is usually framed as innovation. The expected impact here obviously is more productivity and economic growth.⁶ When used in the domain of policymaking, the scientific practice can be called, more accurately, “regulatory science”. Knowledge is translated in the form of expertise and this falls under the framing, broadly, of regulation.⁷ The expected impact here is efficiency, based on sound (for what is often called evidence-based) decision making.

Situated practice: “science for policy” encapsulates different types of interaction between science (scientists) and policymaking (policymakers).⁸ These interactions can be understood as brokering (Pielke, Jr 2007). They are highly situated, that is, they depend on various variables, such as the purpose (ranging from diplomacy, legitimization, to problem apprehension and actual decision-making), various contextual aspects (e.g., is there a crisis? What are the political circumstances of the interaction?), as well as five-W-questions (who is engaged, why is the interaction happening, what is actually discussed, where and when is the interaction taking place?).

⁶ Here, as in the domain of policymaking, other words are also used to describe the expected impact, such as competitiveness, but this exercise aims neither at being comprehensive nor at discussing the nuances of these terminologies

⁷ This is inspired by the reflections by Gil Eyal in his book about the “crisis of expertise” (Eyal 2019).

⁸ Sociological literature on “practice theory” is a good inspiration for this concept (Schatzki 2001; Reckwitz 2002; Knorr Cetina, Schatzki, and Von Savigny 2005).

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Table 2: Dimensions of brokering scientific knowledge and formats of communication

	Informal	Formal
Exchange	Joint problem apprehension	Conference, foresight exercise, ...
Uni-directional	Q&A	Recommendation, commissioned report, statistics

By TK

Probably one reason why many descriptions of “best practices” in scientific advice are mainly anecdotal is because all these variables are highly contingent.⁹ Even in the most formal setting – say, a legally established council that is supposed to meet with policymakers in regular intervals –, some remain unpredictable. And of course, this would be only one of many different types of interactions. Analytically, thus, the most relevant aspect is the “how” – as to, which basic procedural setup is in place for any given interaction (see Table 2). The reason is not that this “how” is more “stable” than the other variables, but that the procedural setup allows to systematically distinguish between two main dimensions of how the science-for-policy interaction is organized, one being the degree of formality of the interaction, the other being whether the advice is taking the form of unidirectional recommendations, or whether it is shaped through an exchange to define the problem at hand.

Communicative acts: About a decade ago, three respected scientists published an article outlining “twenty tips for interpreting scientific claims”, with the ambition “to improve policy-makers’ understanding of the imperfect nature of science.” (Sutherland, Spiegelhalter, and Burgman 2013, 335) Upon media reporting of this list (Milmann 2013), a rebuttal was soon written: “Top 20 things scientists need to know about policy-making” (Tyler 2013). While the two texts are still worthy reading; the anecdote reveals an important though often overlooked fact: “science for policy” is an act of communication.

Since there are different types of interaction possible, “science for policy” entails also different formats of communication, from statistical surveys to commissioned studies, evaluations of policy instruments as well as foresight exercises, and seemingly casual conversations (see Table 2). Each is determined by a core principle of communication theory, that there is a sender and a receiver. Other rules of communication inevitably apply as well (such as Watzlawick’s five axioms). To a great extent, effectiveness of advice relies on the (empathic) capability to convey scientific knowledge in a way that it can be comprehended in the policy realm – or, as it is called elsewhere, “tacit knowledge” (Collins 2010).

“Science for policy” is not a one-model-fit-all; this much is acknowledged by the “ecosystem” extension. The nexus between scientific knowledge and political decision-making is a crucial intersection where “the boundary between science and politics has to be constantly redrawn and reiterated.” (Weingart 1999, 160; similarly, Eyal 2019). As stressed before: to get a better grasp of the “ecosystem”, a focus on various interactions of brokering under the notion of “science for policy” is needed.

Analysing “science for policy” interactions in Austria

This section emphasizes that, in order to improve knowledge utilization in the domain of policymaking in Austria, it is necessary to establish a more self-reflexive mode of learning – both on the sides of scientists and policymakers. Given the communicative situatedness of “science for policy” interactions, a more conscious approach towards learning is one crucial component in that regard. As will be shown, there is already material for such learning available, but it needs to be taken up and channelled into the process of setting up, and revamping “science for policy” interactions.

⁹ This is not to demote anecdotal assessments (such as Gluckman 2014); they are informative and provide crucial insights.

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The case of Austria during the pandemic

As in many other industrialized countries, the pandemic has put the relationship between science and policy under quite some stress; and as elsewhere, this has led to some inflections. The following summary is based on these broader (and more nuanced) studies and reports as well as personal accounts (König 2020; König and Stampfer 2021; Müller 2022; Bogner et al. 2023; Bogner and Buntfuß 2023).

During the pandemic, the “science for policy” ecosystem in Austria had difficulties in adapting and learning. This is best exemplified by the GECKO, a council set up specifically in late 2021 (after almost 18 months of pandemic) with the intention to establish a structure better suited to advise the Austrian government. Interestingly, however, the council was set up along a similar procedural and structural design that had hemmed its predecessors. No space for deliberation was given; experts were expected to answer straight to questions from the government; and council members included not only scientists, but representatives from provincial governments and corporatist partners.¹⁰

This failed experiment, however, does not mean that learning is not possible in the future. So, what insights do existing studies on the topic reveal about the role of scientific advice in Austria? First of all, and maybe surprisingly, Austria has a rich fabric of “science for policy” interactions, based on legal provisions as well as through established institutional and personal relations.¹¹ This fabric, however, is somewhat hidden in Austria, and not documented in a systematic manner.¹²

A more general point, learning from the experience during the pandemic, it seems as if advise structures are often constrained by specific features of the Austrian state, such as its neo-corporatist formation, which regularly involves representatives from those corporatist interest groups in science advice. Another feature is that Austria is a consensus democracy with a relatively compartmentalized federal system, where policymaking is driven often by ministry administration (rather than the legislative branch).¹³

Whether those macrostructural features were directly impacting the very design of “science for policy” structures is hard to tell. In any case, the pandemic revealed little willingness to build up capacities and dedicate resources for establishing relevant formats of communication, incentive structures, and processes that allow for more effective scientific advice.

An analytical agenda

So – what does it take to set up scientific advice structures that prove to be reliable and effective in times of crisis? When it comes to prerequisites to enable scientific advice, Bogner and Buntfuß (2023, 84), make the following points:

- The first, and most basic requirement, is that *advice mechanisms need to be established* and organized in the first place. This includes, of course, also the respective resources (staffing, but also a formal mandate and other legal and practical conditions).
- Next, advice mechanisms need to *allow for pluralism* to be capable of *dealing with* (and comprehending) *the different logics* under which the two worlds of science and policymaking operate.

¹⁰ In fairness, this assessment of GECKO is more bluntly than the studies that have evaluated this experiment (Rakowsky et al. 2023; Bogner and Buntfuß 2023).

¹¹ During the pandemic, for example, a study counted nine different bodies of scientific advice that had supported the federal government, several of which were specifically set up for that purpose (Bogner et al. 2023, 38).

¹² For example, the European Commission has a register of all expert groups that it asks for advice; see <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/expert-groups-register/>

¹³ This paragraph consolidates, with many omissions to nuance, the political science literature on Austria’s distinct form of consociationalism (Luther and Müller 1992; Ennser-Jedenastik 2017; Bußjäger and Eller 2023). To note that, in her article on Austria, Margitta Mätzke (2021) explicitly links Austria’s governance structure to its response to COVID-19. To note here also that, amidst a wave of political scandals recently, some were directly connected to “advice” – although most certainly not with the intention of knowledge utilization (Balluff et al. 2023).

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- In addition, there have to be *practical tools and procedures* in place to *train advice* and to *translate between those two worlds*. Among other aspects, this refers to the formats of communication, as detailed above.
- Finally, the participants (experts) involved in these mechanisms need to *grasp the epistemic relevance* of what they are doing. In other words, they need to understand their role in the process of brokering scientific knowledge to policymakers.

This is an important first step to understanding on what premises “science for policy” interactions can be effective. Austria, of course, is not alone with its pandemic-related inflections. While these bodies are only a part of the types of interactions that have been outlined in the previous section, their analysis provides a fruitful starting point for an analysis of the “science for policy” ecosystem.

Maybe the most thorough composition has been published just recently and comprises several points (see Box 1). It is notable that this list – which certainly is based on a thorough process of reflection by highly respected scientists – brings together behavioural, organizational, and procedural aspects, without making clear that each is to be defined by other actors. In that sense, lists like this certainly provide a comprehensive and useful guideline. However, they only lead so far, disregarding insights related to context and situatedness.

Box 1: Principles for effective scientific councils during pandemic crises

- Include breadth, depth, and diversity of expertise; encourage both constructive challenge and collaborative, interdisciplinary ways of working; and place work from the outset in a possible long-term perspective.
- Be established quickly and adapt as the situation develops; have a formal status.
- Provide decision makers with evidence-based scientific advice for policy rather than determining policy itself.
- Be clear about the quantity and quality of evidence available and the degree of confidence and uncertainty in the conclusions reached.
- Be led by evidence and be politically independent. Councils should maintain a degree of autonomy from decision makers in both their composition and the topics they consider, and should have the possibility of self-tasking.
- Have clear routes to deliver advice to decision makers and to receive questions and feedback; and publicise advice within a short timeframe to health-care providers, the press, and the general public, to maintain and preserve trust between scientists and civil society, which is a fundamental element for citizen resilience.
- Be transparent and communicate effectively scientific advice. Councils should have control over the publication of their outputs.

Source: (Delfraissy et al. 2024, 510)

At least, these insights need to be complemented by comparing a number of case studies of already established bodies of policy advice in Austria. This approach will likely yield insights are relevant for learning how to establish new science-for-policy interactions that are more effective, and maybe also to revamp existing ones.

The proposed analysis is to identify existing bodies and structures of policy advice to the government in Austria, and to survey them along their basic structural and procedural components. As core features, these bodies must fulfil the following criteria: they must be independent (including that their members are not subject to directives); they must be established on a legal basis or have an official mandate; and they must claim to utilize scientific knowledge. While these criteria may seem straight forward at first view, they most likely will turn out to be quite fuzzy. Indeed, the analysis of various bodies will have to show to what extent these criteria can really help identifying the bodies that are out there.

The proposed assessment is not an academic exercise (albeit it might be used in that respect, too), but necessary to continue the process of learning from the studies on Austria mentioned above, broadening to different policy fields and going beyond pandemic-related interactions. It intends to complement lists like the

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one in Box 1 with a qualified evaluation of different types of procedural setup as well as communication formats.

The most important take-away is that, in Austria, the capacity for learning from existing experiences is crucial – and if this has been a weak spot thus far, it should be quickly remedied. Learning includes to provide connections between different “science for policy” interaction (be they formalized or only ad hoc), and also making room for reflection. Notably, FORWIT has an important role to play in this. But it will only be possible if it is supported by those who are within the “science for policy” ecosystem.

Outlook

The main argument of this paper is to emphasize the fact that, when it comes to knowledge utilization in the domain of policymaking, a separate terminology, as well as infrastructure and instruments are in play. Talking of a “science for policy” ecosystem is a good development in principle, but only if it is complemented by a careful examination of the plethora of actual “science for policy” interactions. The ecosystem it is an envelope for those interactions, each of which is highly situated, and therefore can only be routinized to a certain extent.

For Austria, there are already some insightful lessons to learn, and **learning**, really, is key when the ambition is to make those interactions more effective. This final section brings together some ideas for possible instruments, and procedures, that might help to foster the very premises of different types of interactions, thereby improving the entire ecosystem.

Food for discussion

Other than in the previous section, these ideas are not constricted to structures per se; rather, they play into the full bouquet of different “science for policy” interactions. The following is a collection of ideas that have been mentioned in discussions leading up to this paper, or that have been implemented in other ecosystems. Whenever possible, they are connected to existing initiatives, in order to create synergies. Alas, these ideas are only initial input for open discussion, which is about to begin at the upcoming ERA Symposium on 21. November 2024. Most importantly, these ideas are not concerned with “science for policy” interactions per se; instead they aim at **enhancing the advice capacity** of the actors within the ecosystem.

One crucial aspect in that regard concerns the tacit knowledge of how to communicate in situations of advice. This includes a framework for **training knowledge uptake and knowledge communication** between government and academic and research organisations. The newly established “Austrian School of government” might provide the appropriate format for this.¹⁴ In addition, and with the same intention, it could be useful to increase the opportunities to shift temporarily between academic and research positions to positions within the public administration. One instrument to that end could be a **fellowship program**, directed at junior and senior researchers and scientists to be embedded for an extended period (6-12 months) in a specific branch of the administration, according to expertise.¹⁵ Similarly, public servants could be embedded with an analogous program in research organisations. Furthermore, to foster exchange between different actors in the “science for policy” ecosystem, a regular **conference** on “expertise” could be established.¹⁶

While these suggestions aim at creating more space for learning at the level of individual actors involved in “science for policy” interactions, another aspect concerns more comprehensive efforts. The FORWIT’s own ambition to **map scientific advice structures** in Austria (as outlined in the previous section) plays into this topic. In addition, it could be useful to establish a **forum of exchange on best practices in commissioned**

¹⁴ See <https://www.bmkoes.gv.at/asg.html> as well as the report to the council of ministers (Kogler 2021).

¹⁵ See, for example, the U.S.-based program of “White House Fellowships”, <https://www.whitehouse.gov/get-involved/fellows/>.

¹⁶ This could be similar to the well-established Tech Talks that deal with the topic of innovation; see <https://technologytalks.ait.ac.at/>.

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research studies; ideally, this forum includes also experiences from executive agencies as well as research organisations performing commissioned research studies.¹⁷ Furthermore, an interministerial forum on departmental research (“Ressortforschung”) could be tasked to establish **standard rules for regulatory science** projects across the whole government. To assess realistically the scientific capability within the administration, a **“government science capability assessment”** exercise might provide useful insights.¹⁸ To make areas of policymaking transparent where scientific advice is sought, a **registry** similarly to that of the European Commission might be useful (as mentioned in the previous section).

Tentative timeline

This paper is a starting point. It is supposed to kick off a discussion that results in a specific action within the next ERA National Action Plan (NAP). Specifically, the ideas mentioned above are probably only a few out of many other options that this action plan could entail. In the best of all cases, it will stimulate more ideas, which would then have to be discussed and assessed, in order to create a list of ambitious yet realistic goals to be included in the NAP.

To that end, a tentative timeline is outlined in Table 3. As with the suggestions above, this timeline should also be understood as object of discussion for the upcoming ERA Symposium. It might be helpful as a first step to define milestones and clarify the extent and type of contribution needed.

Table 3: Tentative timeline of “Science for Policy” action

Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	March	Apr	May	June	July	Aug
ERA Symposium		Follow-up Workshop					Deadline NAP		
Redrafting White Paper (based on discussion)		Consolidate possible Action Points for NAP				Finalize Input for NAP			

By TK

To wrap up: this paper argues that, in order to make use of the framing of “science for policy” as an ecosystem, it is relevant to focus on existing interactions of scientific advice, and to understand those interactions as situated acts of communication. To make “science for policy” more effective, emphasis should be put on learning opportunities; to that end, the paper offers several ideas that could enhance the advice capacity of actors in the ecosystem. These ideas are to be discussed at the upcoming ERA Symposium on 21 November 2024 in Vienna, which is the starting point for drafting the respective chapter on “science for policy” in the Austrian ERA National Action Plan 2025-27.

¹⁷ In this context, see the “Memorandum of Understanding” on best practices in commissioned research signed by several Austrian research organizations: commissioned research: https://www.ihs.ac.at/fileadmin/public/2016_Files/Documents/2024/memorandum_of_understanding_research_integrity_AIT_IHS_JR_WIFO_final_EN.pdf

¹⁸ The idea for this comes from the British government, which has done a similar exercise twice since 2019 (Government Office for Science 2019; 2024).

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